

ARTS RELATED TO RETURNING WORDS IN THE LYRICS OF ERKIN VAHIDOV

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Abstract: This article provides the analysis of arts which are based on repeating words and illustrates data about the importance of the arts in the poems of "Yoshlik Devoni" by Erkin Vahidov.

Key words: Mutobiqa, Tasdir, Ajuz, Sadr, Hashv, Ibtiqqa, Zarb, Aruz.

In our classical literature, which has a thousand-year history, the issue of artistry has always been the focus of attention of poets. The ability to use poetic arts in literary works has been evaluated as one of the main aspects of artistic artistry in all centuries. It is known that the poetic arts served to make the ideas expressed in the work of art more vivid and impressive, to embody lyrical and epic symbols more vividly, to ensure the verbal elegance, musicality, and appeal of verses, stanzas, and stanzas. One of the types of verbal art, which is based on the repetition of some words in a verse in another place, is the art of repetition. This art, which is considered "one of the most classic and acceptable" among literary arts by the scholar of literature Rashididdin Vatvot, is called radd ul-ajuz il-as-sadr in some of the works on classical literature, mutabiqa in some, and tasdir in some. In classical literature, the beginning of the verse is sadr, the end is ajuz or zarb, the end of the first verse is called aruz, the beginning of the second verse is called ibtida, and the middle of both verses (between sadr and aruz, between the beginning and ajuz) is called hashv.¹

We paid attention to the places where the words are repeated when dividing this verbal art into groups, which is used in the work of Erkin Vahidov, who occupies a worthy place in our modern literature with his works on aruz weight.

¹A. Hojiahmedov. The merit of classical artistry. - Tashkent: Sharq, 1999.

1. Radd ul-aruz ilal-ibtida (return of the word at the end of the first line at the beginning of the next line):

How many thousands of worlds are there in this grain of wheat?

There is how many thousands of cycles load at each point of it.

or:

Love is such a pain that all parts are affected,

Mubtalo It's a crazy thing to do.

2. Radd us-sadr ilal-hashv (return of the word at the beginning of the stanza in the stanza). There are two types of this type:

a) return of "sadr" in the first verse in "hashv" of this verse:

*Eye if i'm sorry eye i'm - my flower face appears in front of me,
A nightingale with a bud in its eyeball.*

b) occurrence of "sadr" after "hashv" in the second line:

Always I said, don't be a fool,

It's enough to constantly worry about the heart.

3. Radd us-sadr ilal-ibtida (the word at the beginning of the stanza is returned at the beginning of the second line):

*Morning no, if I'm in this morning, I'm drowning in dreams,
Morning because my mind is like a dream.*

or:

One It's not a surprise to die in love

One Happy cypress.

4. Radd us-sadr ilal-zarb (ajuz) (the word at the beginning of the byte is returned at the end of the byte):

Leaf I said, but I don't know which one is better.

Two musky sunbulings or two basil leaves.

or:

*Are there stars in your eyes, no, a star shines through every spark,
Look at the scorching sun and the blue sky.*

5. Radd ul-hashwa ilal-hashwa(the occurrence of "hashv" of the first verse in place of "hashv" in this verse or the use of "hashv" in the second verse):

*Bring the petaled tulip, put it next to the glass,
A heart is like blood in a glass in a face.*

or:

*My old city, if I close my eyes to your history, it's a dream
Drowning was seen in the flood of tears of the oppressed people.*

6. Radd ul-aruz ilal-hashv(the occurrence of the word at the end of the first verse after "hashv" in the second verse):

*I wish you a throne of happiness, a crown of lace for your head,
Peace to your property, prosperity to your throne.*

or:

*My eyes always need you,
Tell me, my dear, do you have my eyes?*

7. Radd ul-ibtida ilal-hashav(the occurrence of the word at the beginning of the second verse after "hashv" in this verse):

*Yesterday was the moon, the wavy sea, the cypress that woke up with
a melody,*

Mooncame and landed on a cypress tree, it was a cypress tree.

or:

*It is not morning if Erkin puts the definition of two leaves into a free
poem.*

He is onetashbihli is a leaf, and one is a tajnis leaf.

8. Radd ul-hashwa ilal-ibtida(occurrence of the word in the middle of the first verse at the beginning of the second verse):

*How many dust from Majnun left in the desert of love,
How manyFarhad Gardi lies on the mountain of Bisutun.*

or:

*Killing is at the edge of the spring, combing hair.
FountainHe sees his own reflection in the mirror.*

10. Radd ul-hashwa ilal-zarb (ajuz)(the occurrence of a word in a verse at the end of a stanza):

*I've come to a cypress tree
Tell the world early in the morning, don't do it, cypress.*

or:

*My trembling is like a leaf shaking,
Or a delicate leaf that touches my heart.*

Places related to the art of return presented in these examples, along with increasing the emotional and expressive power of the thought put forward in the poet's lyrics, also performed the task of conveying subtle and hidden aspects of the thought to the readers. Due to his knowledge of classical literature and high vocabulary, Erkin Vahidov was able to skillfully use every repeated word to reveal his artistic purpose. In his work, using one word twice in the same stanza and replacing the rhyme and weight during this is one aspect of the art of radd, but it reflects the second important feature of being able to influence the artistic taste of the reader by showing the special meaning aspects of both repeated words. No matter what kind of restorative arts

The art of repetition serves as a tool in the effective expression of the poet's thought. In this case, attention is paid to a specific word or phrase, and through it it is intended to emphasize the logical emphasis. The methodological load expressing the main goal is placed on these words or phrases. In addition, by repeating words, the writer can set different artistic goals. For example, considering that these words combine different shades of meaning around them, there is also the possibility of creating a special playfulness with the help of their repetition in one stanza. A poet can express his creative power through the appropriate use of any type of art form.

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